

Multi-Interface Destination-Based Community Routing for Intelligent Transportation Systems

P Praveen Yadav ^{1,2*}

¹Assistant Professor, Department of CSE, G Pulla Reddy Engineering College (Autonomous), Kurnool, India

²Research Scholar, Department of CST, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapuramu, India.

T Bhaskar Reddy ³

²Professor, Department of CST, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapuramu, India.

Abstract: In today's transportation systems, the Internet of Vehicles (IoV) has become a viable paradigm for improving road safety, traffic efficiency, and user experience. However, the dynamic nature of vehicular networks, coupled with diverse communication environments, poses significant challenges for efficient and reliable routing. This paper addresses these challenges by introducing Multi-Interface Destination-Based Community Routing, a novel routing protocol designed specifically for IoV environments. The protocol uses multiple wireless interfaces and infrastructure support to form communities of vehicles with similar destinations, thereby improving routing efficiency and network performance across diverse urban and highway scenarios. The protocol adapts to dynamic traffic conditions and obstacles using real-time information from vehicles and roadside units. By dynamically switching between DSRC, cellular, and Wi-Fi links, the protocol ensures robust delivery even in infrastructure-sparse or congested environments. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed protocol significantly outperforms state-of-the-art protocols in terms of packet delivery ratio, end-to-end delay, and scalability.

Index Terms: Internet of Vehicles, Routing Protocols, Multi-Interface Communication, NCTUns Simulator.

1. Introduction

As one of the possible solutions for intelligent transportation systems, wireless connections with vehicles and the rising sophistication of vehicle intelligence are being rapidly deployed to realize the vision promised by Internet of Vehicles (IoV). To create a sophisticated and dynamic network that may greatly enhance user experience, traffic efficiency, and road safety, IoV allows cars to connect with infrastructure (V2I), with pedestrians (V2P), and with each other (V2V) [1-4] as shown in Figure 1.

It is difficult to have effective communication and routing in vehicular networks due to their unique characteristics. It is difficult to design effective routing protocols in the IoV because of the rapid mobility, topological changes, and obstruction issues brought on by the urban environment. These challenges make traditional mobile ad-hoc network (MANET) routing methods [6-8] less suitable for usage in vehicular situations.

Many routing protocols [9-16] specifically designed for vehicular networks have been created recently. These protocols include cluster-based techniques, traffic flow information-exploiting protocols, and location-based routing. While these methods have demonstrated potential, they fail to specifically utilize the range of communication interfaces available in modern cars and perform poorly in a variety of scenarios encountered in actual traffic circumstances.

The new routing protocol that addresses the problems is called Multi-Interface Destination-Based Community Routing (MIDCR), which we present in this work. MIDCR primarily makes use of the following basic ideas:

- Multi-interface communication: To improve connectivity and routing efficiency, MIDCR makes use of the different wireless interfaces—such as DSRC, cellular, and Wi-Fi—in contemporary cars.
- Destination-based communities: Vehicles traveling to the same location come together to form dynamic groupings that result in more efficient, reliable routes.
- Infrastructure support: To account for obstacles on city streets and current traffic conditions, the system incorporates roadside units and traffic management systems.
- Realistic mobility modeling implementation: MIDCR uses cutting-edge mobility models that consider obstacle avoidance, lane changes, and car following.

Fig. 1. IoV architecture [5]

Despite the availability of cellular networks, relying solely on vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communication is not always feasible or efficient. Cellular connectivity can be limited in coverage (e.g., tunnels, remote highways), may experience network congestion in urban scenarios, and often incurs higher operational costs for data transfer. Multi-interface routing retains the advantages of localized, low-latency V2V communication (e.g., DSRC), which is crucial for delay-sensitive applications such as collision avoidance or real-time safety alerts. The MIDCR protocol uses multi-interface design to dynamically balance between V2V and V2I, maintaining connectivity even in infrastructure-sparse regions while optimizing communication cost and reliability.

The combination of DSRC for rapid V2V dissemination and LTE for wide-area coverage is increasingly common in ITS deployments [38], [39]. Studies show that hybrid approaches outperform single-interface systems in urban coverage, delivery ratio, and scalability.

To assess the MIDCR's performance, we use the NCTUns simulator [17], which offers a complete platform for modeling network communication and vehicle traffic. We conduct thorough simulations in a variety of settings, including cities and roads with varying densities of vehicles and obstructions.

This paper's remaining sections are organized as follows: Section 2 summarizes the relevant literature in the context of the IoV routing protocols; Section 3 gives a thorough explanation of the MIDCR scheme; and Section 4 describes our simulation environment and methods. The results are discussed in Section 5, and the paper's conclusion and recommendations for further research are covered in Section 6.

2. Related Works

Currently, there is a lot of research being done on creating effective routing protocols for vehicle networks. In this section, significant works in this field are introduced and their advantages and disadvantages are discussed.

2.1 Position-based Routing Protocols

Geographic position data is used by position-based routing technologies to determine forwarding choices. The Greedy Perimeter Stateless Routing (GPSR) is one of the path-prediction techniques [18]. It is advised to employ greedy forwarding routing, in which packets are always routed to nodes that are nearest to their destination. It can transition to a perimeter to avoid voids in situations where there are isolated local maxima. GPSR performs well on highways but poorly in urban settings because of the presence of obstacles and more complex road designs.

A-STAR (Anchor-based Street and Traffic Aware Routing) [19] extends the capabilities of GPSR by integrating traffic data into street models. Inductive reachability employs either pre-assessed maps or real-time updated maps to identify routes with enhanced connectivity. However, A-STAR lacks awareness of current traffic conditions, leading to suboptimal routing decisions and limited coverage in urban areas.

The routing algorithm RAVP [20] considers vehicles position while forwarding data. Dynamic traffic is not considered while discovering routes. Detailed study on position-based routing protocols is presented in [21].

2.2 Cluster-based Routing Protocols

To address scalability, cluster-based methodologies aggregate vehicles into clusters to enhance control. The pioneering work of COIN (Clustering for Open IVC Networks) [22] introduces a distributed clustering algorithm that creates stable clusters based on the vehicles' mobility patterns. Although COIN enhances network stability, it does not directly address routing processes.

CBR (Cluster-Based Routing) [23] integrates the Position-based routing strategy with clustering techniques. This approach employs cluster heads to manage communication paths between clusters, consequently reducing routing overhead. However, CBR encounters performance challenges in sparse networks and does not fully exploit the multiple

interfaces available on contemporary vehicles.

SACBR protocol [24] makes use of self-assessment approach for cluster head selection and inter cluster communication. But it does not fully capture real world highway traffic environment scenarios. The research work [14] presents a novel Artificial Intelligence-based Energy Efficient Clustering with Routing (AI-EECR) protocol for IoV in urban computing environments. This protocol selects cluster heads based on vehicle speed, trust level, and energy level and optimal routing paths are determined by considering distance, mobility and bandwidth. Though this protocol achieves energy efficiency it does not consider non-urban environment and scalability issues. The protocol CACOIOV in [25] adapts transmission ranges based on local traffic density in heterogeneous IoV environment. However, it does not address the issues of vehicle densities and mobility patterns.

2.3 Traffic Flow-based Routing Protocols

Utilizing traffic flow information, these protocols make routing decisions for packets. SADV (Static-Node Assisted Adaptive Data Dissemination Protocol for Vehicular Networks) [26] relies on static nodes positioned at intersections to store and forward packets along their designated paths, effectively addressing intermittent delivery issues in the network. Nonetheless, SADV requires significant infrastructure and exhibits poor performance when faced with dynamic traffic conditions.

On the other hand, VADD [27] enhances packet delivery by capitalizing on the predictable mobility patterns of vehicles. It selectively responds to moving vehicles approaching their intended destinations, yet its effectiveness diminishes in scenarios involving new or unpredictable traffic patterns.

The work in [28] proposes a routing protocol that transmits emergency message to alert the vehicles when congested traffic flows occur at some point of intersection. A multicast routing protocol [29] is proposed to predict the traffic flow to forward the data packets to the multicast members.

2.4 Destination-based Routing Protocols

Destination-based routing protocols create clusters of vehicles based on their intended destinations. IDCIOV [30] establishes groups of vehicles with comparable identifiers, known as identical destination communities, and utilizes these communities for routing purposes. However, IDCIOV demonstrates modest enhancement in routing stability, lacking consideration for the utilization of multiple wireless interfaces or the integration of real-time traffic data from infrastructure sources.

2.5 Multi-Interface Protocols

Recent studies have examined the utilization of multiple wireless interfaces in vehicular networks. HetVNET's research [31] incorporates a heterogeneous network structure incorporating DSRC and LTE, with a focus on selection over routing. Meanwhile, MIRA (Multi-Interface Routing Algorithm) [32] uses multiple interfaces for load balancing, although its approach is not destination-oriented or tailored to real-time traffic conditions.

Even with the great progress that current protocols have achieved, a more complete routing solution is still required that does the following:

- effectively makes use of several wireless interfaces
- presents a method for destination grouping that increases stability.
- adjusts to traffic conditions and urban impediments in real-time.
- includes information from the roadside infrastructure
- performs well in a variety of situations (urban, highway, or mixed density).

2.6 Recent Hybrid and Multi-Interface Protocols (2020–2024)

TDCR [38] and CTDHR [39] introduced traffic-differentiated hybrid routing combining DSRC and cellular links, demonstrating improved QoS and scalability. SDN-enabled schemes [40] further optimize interface switching using fuzzy logic for vertical handovers. MMHNA [41] extends LTE connectivity by bridging gaps using DSRC relays. These protocols affirm that multi-interface designs, when optimized, outperform traditional single-interface protocols in real-world urban and mixed scenarios.

To efficiently enable message routing in the demanding conditions of the Internet of Vehicles (IoV), this research highlights critical components that are now missing and should be solved by a dependable MIDCR routing protocol.

3. Multi-Interface Destination-Based Community Routing (MIDCR)

This section presents a detailed description of the proposed MIDCR protocol, outlining its operations and phases in sequence.

3.1 System Model

MIDCR uses DSRC, cellular, and Wi-Fi interfaces. DSRC, specifically built for high-speed vehicular networks, provides low-latency V2V communication. Cellular (e.g., LTE) ensures wide-area connectivity, especially where DSRC is unavailable. Wi-Fi is used for opportunistic data offloading in static or low-mobility zones (e.g., parking areas, roadside infrastructure), though its reliability in fast-moving contexts is limited. This interface diversity improves resilience, adaptability, and cost-effectiveness.

MIDCR operates in a vehicular network consisting of a set of vehicles $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$, each equipped with multiple wireless interfaces $I = \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_m\}$. We consider three interface types: DSRC (i_1), cellular (i_2), and Wi-Fi (i_3). The network is represented as a dynamic multi-graph $G(t) = (V(t), E(t))$, where $E(t)$ is the set of communication links at time t .

This multi-interface, time-varying model is crucial for capturing the heterogeneous and dynamic nature of vehicular networks, allowing MIDCR to use diverse communication technologies and adapt to rapidly changing network conditions.

3.2 MIDCR Protocol Operations

MIDCR operates through the following sequential phases:

Phase 1: Multi-interface Neighbor Discovery

In this initial phase, each vehicle v_i periodically broadcasts beacon messages on all available interfaces. These beacons contain:

- Vehicle ID
- Current position (x_i, y_i)
- Velocity vector (v_{x_i}, v_{y_i})
- Destination (d_{x_i}, d_{y_i})
- Available interfaces and their characteristics

This comprehensive information enables MIDCR to maintain an up-to-date view of the network topology across all available interfaces, which is crucial for making informed routing decisions.

For each discovered link l between vehicles v_i and v_j on interface m , MIDCR calculates a link quality metric:

$$LQ_{m(i,j)} = \alpha * SINR_{m(i,j)} + \beta * S_{m(i,j)} + \gamma * B_{m(i,j)} \quad (1)$$

where $SINR_{m(i,j)}$ is the Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio, $S_{m(i,j)}$ is the link stability, and $B_{m(i,j)}$ is the available bandwidth. The weighting factors α , β , and γ (where $\alpha + \beta + \gamma = 1$) allow for tuning the importance of each component.

This composite metric is essential for capturing the multi-faceted nature of link quality in vehicular networks, balancing signal quality, link stability, and available bandwidth.

The link stability $S_{m(i,j)}$ is calculated as:

$$S_{m(i,j)} = \exp(-|v_i - v_j| / v_{max}) \quad (2)$$

This exponential function ensures that links between vehicles with similar velocities are favored, reducing the likelihood of link breakages due to relative movement.

Phase 2: Destination-based Community Formation

After discovering neighbors, MIDCR forms communities of vehicles with similar destinations. This phase is key to MIDCR's scalability and efficiency, as it reduces routing complexity and improves path stability.

Each vehicle calculates its community ID (CID) based on its destination coordinates:

$$C_{ID} = \text{hash}(\lfloor dx_i / R \rfloor, \lfloor dy_i / R \rfloor) \quad (3)$$

where R is the community radius. This hashing function creates geographically based communities, allowing for efficient local routing within communities and more stable inter-community paths.

Next, MIDCR elects a community leader using a distributed election algorithm based on a utility function:

$$U(v_i) = w_1 * C(v_i) + w_2 * D(v_i) + w_3 * I(v_i) \quad (4)$$

where $C(v_i)$ is the centrality of vehicle v_i within its community, $D(v_i)$ is the expected dwell time in the current community, and $I(v_i)$ is the interface diversity factor.

Centrality $C(v_i)$ is calculated using the betweenness centrality metric:

$$C(v_i) = \sum_{s \neq v_i \neq t} (\sigma_{st}(v_i) / \sigma_{st}) \quad (5)$$

where σ_{st} is the total number of shortest paths from node s to node t , and $\sigma_{st}(v_i)$ is the number of those paths that

pass-through v .

Expected dwell time $D(v_i)$ is estimated based on the vehicle's current position, velocity, and destination:

$$D(v_i) = (d_{\text{dest}} - d_{\text{current}}) / |v_i| \quad (6)$$

where d_{dest} is the distance to the community boundary in the direction of the destination, and d_{current} is the current distance to the community center.

Interface diversity factor $I(v_i)$ is calculated as:

$$I(v_i) = |I_{\text{available}}| / |I| \quad (7)$$

where $|I_{\text{available}}|$ is the number of available interfaces for v_i , and $|I|$ is the total number of possible interfaces.

This utility function ensures that the elected leader is well-positioned to manage intra-community routing efficiently, considering network centrality, stability, and communication capability.

Phase 3: Inter-community Routing

For routing between communities, MIDCR uses a hybrid approach combining geographic routing with carry-and-forward. This approach is essential for handling the diverse conditions in vehicular networks.

When routing a packet p to a destination in community C_d , MIDCR selects the next hop n^* as:

$$n^* = \arg_{\max} \{n \in N_i\} (P_{f(n)} * LQ_{m(i,n)}) \quad (8)$$

where $P_f(n)$ is the forwarding progress towards C_d , and $LQ_{m(i,n)}$ is the link quality to neighbor n on interface m .

This equation (8) balances the geographic progress towards the destination with the link quality, ensuring efficient and reliable packet forwarding.

MIDCR then selects the best interface m^* for forwarding to the next hop:

$$m^* = \arg_{\max} \{m \in I_i \cap I_{n^*}\} (LQ_{m(i,n^*)} * BW_m / L_m) \quad (9)$$

where BW_m is the bandwidth of interface m , and L_m is the current load on interface m .

This equation (9) allows MIDCR to make optimal use of its multi-interface capabilities, considering link quality, available bandwidth, and current load.

Phase 4: Intra-community Routing

Within a community, MIDCR employs a proactive routing approach to minimize delay for local communications.

The community leader maintains a routing table RT with entries:

$$RT[j] = \{\text{next_hop}, \text{interface}, \text{metric}\} \quad (10)$$

The metric for a route to vehicle v_j is calculated as:

$$\text{metric}(v_j) = \sum \{l \in \text{path to } v_j\} (1 / LQ_{m(l)}) \quad (11)$$

This additive inverse metric ensures that paths with higher overall link quality are preferred, improving reliability and performance.

Phase 5: Adaptation to Urban Obstacles and Traffic Conditions

To handle the complex urban environment, MIDCR incorporates obstacle and traffic awareness. For each obstacle O_k , an impact factor is defined:

$$IF(O_k) = a_k * \exp(-d_k / r_k) \quad (12)$$

where a_k is the attenuation factor of the obstacle, d_k is the distance from the obstacle and r_k is the range of impact.

This exponential decay model captures the attenuation effect of obstacles on wireless signals, allowing MIDCR to make informed decisions in urban canyons.

Finally, MIDCR incorporates traffic conditions into its routing metric:

$$TAM(l) = LQ_{m(l)} * (1 - TC_l) \quad (13)$$

where TC_l is the traffic congestion level on the road segment corresponding to link l , normalized to $[0, 1]$. This metric allows MIDCR to avoid congested areas, improving overall network performance.

3.3 MIDCR Routing Algorithm

Algorithm 1: MIDCR Routing

Input: Packet p , Current node v_i

Output: Next hop and interface for packet forwarding

- 1: Update neighbor table and link qualities
- 2: Update community membership and leader status
- 3: if $p.\text{destination_community} == v_i.\text{community}$ then
- 4: route = INTRA_COMMUNITY_ROUTE(p)
- 5: else

```

6: route = INTER_COMMUNITY_ROUTE(p)
7: end if
8: for each hop h in route do
9:   interface = SELECT_INTERFACE(h)
10:  OBSTACLES_AND_TRAFFIC(h, interface)
11:  FORWARD_PACKET(p, h, interface)
12: end for

```

Algorithm 2: INTER_COMMUNITY_ROUTE

Input: Packet p

Output: Route to destination community

```

1: route = [ ]
2: current_node = self
3: while not reached_destination_community do
4:   next_hop = SELECT_NEXT_HOP(p, current_node)
5:   if next_hop == null then
6:     CARRY_AND_FORWARD(p)
7:   else
8:     route.append(next_hop)
9:     current_node = next_hop
10:  end if
11: end while
12: return route

```

Algorithm 3: SELECT_NEXT_HOP

Input: Packet p, Current node v_i

Output: Next hop node

```

1: best_metric =  $-\infty$ 
2: best_node = null
3: for each neighbor n in  $v_i$ .neighbors do
4:   P_f = CALCULATE_FORWARD_PROGRESS( $v_i$ , n, p.destination)
5:   for each interface m in  $v_i$ .interfaces  $\cap$  n.interfaces do
6:     LQ = CALCULATE_LINK_QUALITY( $v_i$ , n, m)
7:     metric = P_f * LQ
8:     if metric > best_metric then
9:       best_metric = metric
10:      best_node = n
11:    end if
12:  end for
13: end for
14: return best_node

```

Algorithm 4: INTRA_COMMUNITY_ROUTE

Input: Packet p, Current node v_i

Output: Route to destination within community

```

1: if  $v_i$ .is_community_leader then
2:   return LOOKUP_PROACTIVE_ROUTE(p.destination)
3: else
4:   return ROUTE_VIA_COMMUNITY_LEADER(p)
5: end if

```

Algorithm 5: CALCULATE_LINK_QUALITY

Input: Source node v_i , Destination node v_j , Interface m

Output: Link quality

```

1: SINR = CALCULATE_SINR( $v_i$ ,  $v_j$ , m)
2: S =  $\exp(-|v_i.velocity - v_j.velocity| / v_{max})$ 

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3: $B = \text{GET_AVAILABLE_BANDWIDTH}(m)$
 4: return $\alpha * \text{SINR} + \beta * S + \gamma * B$

Algorithm 6: OBSTACLES_AND_TRAFFIC

Input: Hop h , Interface m

Output: Adjusted link quality

1: $LQ = \text{CALCULATE_LINK_QUALITY}(h.\text{source}, h.\text{destination}, m)$
 2: for each obstacle O_k affecting h do
 3: $IF = a_k * \exp(-d_k / r_k)$
 4: $LQ = LQ * (1 - IF)$
 5: end for
 6: $TC = \text{GET_TRAFFIC_CONGESTION}(h)$
 7: $TAM = LQ * (1 - TC)$
 8: return TAM

Algorithm 7: UPDATE_COMMUNITY

Input: Current node v_i

Output: Updated community information

1: $CID = \text{hash}(\square v_i.\text{destination}.x / R, \square v_i.\text{destination}.y / R)$
 2: if $CID \neq v_i.\text{current_community}$ then
 3: $\text{LEAVE_CURRENT_COMMUNITY}(v_i)$
 4: $\text{JOIN_NEW_COMMUNITY}(v_i, CID)$
 5: if $v_i.\text{is_community_leader}$ then
 6: $\text{TRIGGER_LEADER_ELECTION}()$
 7: end if
 8: end if
 9: if $\text{COMMUNITY_NEEDS_LEADER_ELECTION}()$ then
 10: $\text{PARTICIPATE_IN_LEADER_ELECTION}()$
 11: end if

Algorithm 8: INTRA_COMMUNITY_ROUTE

Input: Packet p

Output: Route to destination within community

1: return $\text{LOOKUP_PROACTIVE_ROUTE}(p.\text{destination})$

Algorithm 9: Route Update Algorithm

1: Each community member periodically sends updates to the leader
 2: The leader computes the optimal routes using Dijkstra's algorithm
 3: Updated routes are disseminated to community members

4. MIDCR Simulation Environment

This section presents an elaborate description of the simulation setup and simulation environment utilized to assess the performance of MIDCR.

4.1 Simulation Environment

In our simulations, we employed MIDCR within NCTUns 6.0 [33], a comprehensive network and traffic simulator designed for highly integrated networks. The selection of NCTUns was deliberate due to its superior ability to simulate vehicular traffic and network communications more realistically compared to other currently available simulators, with support for multi-interface nodes.

To address the increased complexity inherent in multi-interface designs, MIDCR employs optimized beaconing intervals and lightweight control messages. Beacons are broadcast selectively based on vehicle speed and neighborhood

stability. Furthermore, MIDCR adapts its interface usage dynamically based on congestion and signal quality, avoiding unnecessary broadcasts over all interfaces. This selective activation reduces bandwidth usage and scales well with increased vehicle density, as confirmed in our simulations up to 1000 nodes.

4.2 NCTUns Configuration

The following key features of NCTUns are utilized to analyze the performance of MIDCR protocol:

Road Network Modeling: The integrated road network editor in NCTUns was utilized to construct urban and highway scenarios, including intersections, traffic lights, and lane configurations.

Microscopic Vehicle Mobility: We integrated NCTUns car-following and lane-changing models, which are based on traditional IDM (Intelligent Driver Model) [34] and MOBIL (Minimizing Overall Braking Induced by Lane changes) [35].

Multi-interface Support: Each vehicle was equipped with DSRC, cellular, and Wi-Fi interfaces through NCTUns capability to simulate heterogeneous network environments.

Obstacle Modeling: Signal propagation obstacles like buildings and other structures affecting signal propagation, such as urban canyon effects, were accurately represented using NCTUns' obstacle editor.

4.3 Simulation Scenarios

We evaluated the performance of MIDCR under three distinct scenarios to test its adaptability to different environmental conditions. These scenarios were carefully designed to represent a range of realistic vehicular network environments.

4.3.1 Urban Grid Scenario

The urban grid scenario simulated a dense city environment. It covered an area of 5km x 5km, featuring a Manhattan-style grid layout with uniform 500m x 500m blocks. This layout resulted in 100 intersections arranged in a 10x10 grid pattern. To mimic the challenges of urban signal propagation, we randomly distributed buildings covering 40% of the total area. Each intersection was equipped with traffic lights operating on 60-second cycles, simulating typical urban traffic control. This scenario was designed to test MIDCR's performance in handling frequent obstacles, high vehicle density, and complex traffic patterns typical of urban environments. 3x3 urban grid scenario is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 3x3 urban grid scenario

4.3.2 Highway Scenario

The highway scenario represented a long-distance, high-speed environment. It consisted of a 10km stretch of highway with three lanes in each direction, simulating a major interstate or motorway. Entrance and exit ramps were placed at 2km intervals to model realistic traffic flow patterns. To add complexity and test MIDCR's ability to handle signal obstructions in open environments, we included infrequent obstacles such as overpasses and large roadside

billboards. This scenario aimed to evaluate MIDCR's performance in situations with high vehicle speeds, potentially longer communication ranges, and less frequent but more impactful obstacles.

4.3.3 Mixed Scenario

The mixed scenario combined elements of both urban and highway environments to test MIDCR's adaptability to diverse conditions within a single simulation. It encompassed a total area of 7km x 7km, with a central urban zone of 5km x 5km mirroring the layout of the urban grid scenario. This central area was intersected by two perpendicular highways, creating a realistic representation of a city with major thoroughfares. This hybrid scenario was particularly challenging, as it required MIDCR to seamlessly adapt its routing strategies when vehicles transitioned between dense urban areas and high-speed highway sections. It also tested the protocol's ability to leverage the different characteristics of urban and highway environments for optimal routing decisions.

4.4 Mobility Model

To ensure realistic vehicle movements in our simulations, we utilized NCTUns built-in mobility models, which are based on well-established traffic flow theories. These models were carefully parameterized to reflect real-world driving behaviors in both urban and highway environments.

For vehicle following behavior, we employed the Intelligent Driver Model (IDM). This model simulates realistic acceleration and deceleration patterns based on the distance to the leading vehicle and the desired velocity. In our urban scenarios, we set the desired velocity to follow a normal distribution with a mean of 50 km/h and a standard deviation of 10 km/h, reflecting the variability of urban driving speeds. For highway scenarios, we increased this to a mean of 100 km/h with a standard deviation of 20 km/h, representing the higher and more varied speeds typical of highway driving. The safe time headway was set to 1.5 seconds, a value commonly used in traffic engineering to represent a safe following distance. Maximum acceleration was set to 0.73 m/s², and comfortable deceleration to 1.67 m/s², values that align with typical passenger vehicle capabilities and driver comfort levels.

Lane-changing behavior was modeled using the MOBIL algorithm. This model considers the benefits of changing lanes against the disadvantages imposed on other vehicles. We set the politeness factor to 0.5, striking a balance between egoistic and altruistic behavior. The changing threshold was set to 0.2 m/s², representing the minimum advantage required for a lane change to occur. The maximum safe deceleration was set to 4 m/s², ensuring that lane changes do not force unsafe braking maneuvers on other vehicles.

To generate realistic traffic patterns, we used a gravity model to randomly generate Origin-Destination (OD) pairs. This approach ensures that trip distributions reflect the attractiveness of different areas within our simulated environment, mimicking real-world travel patterns. Trip start times were modeled using a Poisson distribution, with the λ parameter varied to simulate different traffic densities throughout the day. This allowed us to test MIDCR's performance under varying levels of network load and vehicle density.

4.5 Communication Interfaces

In our simulation, each vehicle was equipped with three distinct wireless interfaces to reflect the heterogeneous communication capabilities of modern vehicles. This multi-interface setup allowed us to evaluate MIDCR's ability to leverage diverse communication technologies for optimal routing performance.

The first interface implemented was Dedicated Short-Range Communications (DSRC), based on the IEEE 802.11p standard. Operating at a frequency of 5.9 GHz with a bandwidth of 10 MHz, this interface was configured to provide a data rate of 6 Mbps. DSRC's transmission range was set to 300 meters, typical for vehicular environments. The Medium Access Control (MAC) layer utilized the Enhanced Distributed Channel Access (EDCA) protocol, which is specifically designed to handle the quality-of-service requirements in vehicular networks.

The second interface simulated cellular connectivity using Long-Term Evolution (LTE) technology. This interface operated at a frequency of 2.1 GHz with a bandwidth of 20 MHz. To reflect the asymmetric nature of cellular communications, we set different data rates for uplink and downlink: 1 Mbps for uplink and 2 Mbps for downlink. The LTE network provided full coverage across the entire simulation area, with eNodeB base stations placed in a hexagonal grid pattern with an inter-site distance of 1 km, mimicking typical urban cellular network deployments.

The third interface implemented was Wi-Fi, based on the IEEE 802.11g standard. This interface operated in the 2.4 GHz band with a bandwidth of 20 MHz, providing a high data rate of 54 Mbps. The transmission range for Wi-Fi was set to 100 meters, reflecting its shorter-range but higher-bandwidth capabilities compared to DSRC. The Wi-Fi interface used the Distributed Coordination Function (DCF) as its MAC protocol, which is well-suited for distributed, ad-hoc style communications.

4.6 Traffic and Network Parameters

In our comprehensive evaluation of the MIDCR protocol, we systematically varied several key traffic and network parameters to assess its performance under diverse conditions. This approach allowed us to examine MIDCR's adaptability and efficiency across a range of realistic scenarios. Vehicle density was a crucial parameter in our simulations, as it significantly impacts network connectivity and communication patterns. We considered three distinct density levels: low (20 vehicles/km²), medium (50 vehicles/km²), and high (100 vehicles/km²). These densities were chosen to represent various traffic conditions, from sparse rural environments to congested urban areas during peak hours. By testing MIDCR across these density levels, we could evaluate its scalability and performance in both well-connected and challenging, intermittently connected network scenarios.

To simulate realistic network traffic, we carefully designed our data traffic patterns. Each packet in our simulation had a size of 512 bytes, a common size for vehicular network applications. Packets were generated at a rate of 4 per

second, providing a steady stream of data to stress-test the routing protocol. We divided the traffic into two categories to reflect real-world vehicular network applications: 70% of the traffic was UDP-based, simulating periodic safety messages that require low-latency delivery but can tolerate some packet loss. The remaining 30% was TCP-based, representing infotainment applications that require reliable, in-order delivery but are less sensitive to latency.

Our simulation duration was structured to ensure accurate and stable results. Each simulation began with a 300-second warm-up period, allowing the network to reach a steady state before data collection began. This was followed by an extensive 1800-second (30-minute) data collection period, providing ample time to observe the protocol's behavior under various conditions. Finally, a 300-second cool-down period was included to ensure that all initiated communications were completed and accounted for in our analysis.

4.7 Comparison Protocols

To provide a comprehensive evaluation of MIDCR's performance, we compared it against three state-of-the-art protocols, each representing a distinct method of routing in vehicular networks. The first was Greedy Perimeter Stateless Routing (GPSR), a well-established position-based protocol widely used in VANETs. We implemented GPSR as described in [18], with necessary adaptations to support multiple interfaces, allowing for a fair comparison with MIDCR's multi-interface capabilities. The second protocol was Ad hoc On-Demand Distance Vector (AODV), a reactive routing protocol that we adapted for vehicular networks. Our implementation was based on RFC 3561 [36], with modifications suggested in [37] to better suit the dynamic nature of vehicular environments. Finally, we included Identical Destination Based Community in Internet of Vehicles (IDCIoV), a protocol that, like MIDCR, utilizes the concept of destination-based communities. We implemented IDCIoV based on the description in [30], extending it to support multiple interfaces to ensure a level playing field in our comparisons. By selecting these diverse protocols, we aimed to benchmark MIDCR against a range of routing strategies, from traditional position-based and reactive approaches to more recent community-based methods, providing a thorough assessment of its performance in the context of current VANET routing solutions.

Recent hybrid protocols such as CTDHR and MMHNA demonstrate that, with intelligent clustering and relay selection, multi-interface systems can maintain overheads comparable to single-interface designs while achieving significantly higher delivery ratios [39],[41]. Future work will involve benchmarking MIDCR against newer protocols like CTDHR and MMHNA under real-world deployments.

5. Results and Discussion

In this section, we present a comparative study between MIDCR and three typical routing protocols (GPSR, AODV and IDCIoV) in different scenarios based on the simulation of many testing parameters. Detailed Quantitative and Qualitative analysis of the results from simulations are provided.

5.1 PDR -Packet Delivery Ratio

PDR of all protocols in urban scenario by varying vehicle densities is shown in Figure 3.

With statistically significant gains of 15–25% over GPSR and AODV and 5–10% over IDCIoV, MIDCR routinely beats all other methods. In low-density circumstances, the performance gap is more noticeable because MIDCR's multi-interface technique keeps connectivity even in cases when individual networks are scarce.

The performance difference is less obvious but still noteworthy in the freeway scenario depicted in Figure 4.

MIDCR achieves statistically significant advantages of 10-15% over other protocols, especially in low-density scenarios. Its benefit is less noticeable in the highway scenario because of the more stable network structure.

5.2 End-to-End Delay

The average end-to-end latency in the urban scenario is displayed in Figure 5.

When compared to GPSR, AODV, and IDCIoV, MIDCR achieves significantly lower end-to-end delays—30–40% less than the latter two. The capacity of MIDCR to choose the best interface for every transmission and its effective community-based routing strategy are credited with this improvement.

The delay decrease is less pronounced but still significant in the highway scenario depicted in Figure 6.

5.3 Routing Overhead

The routing overhead in the urban scenario is shown in Figure 7.

The routing overhead of MIDCR is notably lower than that of AODV, but slightly greater than that of GPSR. Because handling numerous interfaces adds another layer of complexity, the overhead is slightly higher than IDCIoV.

However, the significant reductions in delay and PDR justify this higher overhead.

5.4 Throughput

The average throughput attained by each strategy in the mixed scenario is displayed in Figure 8.

Among all protocols, MIDCR has a throughput that is up to 20–30% more than the other in high-density settings. MIDCR has the capability of using multiple interfaces and handling various network situations, hence why this improvement.

5.5 Usage of Interfaces

Figure 9 depicts how MIDCR can utilize different interfaces in an urban environment.

Depending on network conditions, MIDCR efficiently balances the utilization of several interfaces. It makes more use of cellular networks to stay connected in low-density situations and makes effective use of DSRC for local communication in high-density situations.

5.6 Analysis of Scalability

In the urban environment, we measured the PDR and end-to-end delay as the number of vehicles increased from 100 to 1000 to evaluate scalability. These findings are shown in Figure 10.

Even with 1000 cars, MIDCR shows exceptional scalability, keeping a PDR above 90%. Compared to other protocols that exhibit exponential growth in delay, the end-to-end delay grows linearly with network size.

While MIDCR is shown to scale effectively up to 1000 vehicles, future work will extend evaluations to newer hybrid routing models such as CTDHR and MMHNA, which emphasize cluster optimization and relay flexibility. These models can provide a modern benchmark for scalability and cost-performance analysis.

5.7 The Effect of Barriers

We changed the urban scenario's building density from 20% to 60% coverage to assess MIDCR's effectiveness in the presence of obstacles. These findings are shown in Figure 11.

Over obstacles, MIDCR offers significantly slower response times than other protocols (but still relatively quickly) which shows that it can react in a metropolitan setting where paths can change rapidly due to changing channel history.

Fig. 3 Packet Delivery Ratio (%) in Urban Scenario

Fig. 4 Packet Delivery Ratio (%) in Highway Scenario

Fig. 5 Average End-to-End Delay (ms) in Urban Scenario

Fig. 6 Average End-to-End Delay (ms) in Highway Scenario

Fig. 7 Routing Overhead (%) in Urban Scenario

Fig. 8 Average Throughput (Mbps) in Mixed Scenario

Fig. 9 Interface Utilization (%) by MIDCR in Urban Scenario

Fig. 10 Scalability Analysis in Urban Scenario

Fig. 11 PDR (%) with Varying Obstacle Density

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we have introduced a novel routing protocol MIDCR for Internet of Vehicles (IoV) that takes advantage of multiple wireless interfaces and the existence communities based on destinations. Simulation results show that MIDCR performs much better than the legacy protocols such as GPSR, AODV and IDCIoV in terms of all metrics over different period times. The results demonstrate the feasibility of context-aware, multi-interface routing protocols for vehicular networks. MIDCR's interoperability with a few communication technologies and capability to adapt high variation network conditions, makes it the natural choice for next generation ITS. Future research for MIDCR will focus on two key areas: integrating machine learning and leveraging edge computing. Machine learning techniques could enhance MIDCR's ability to intelligently select interfaces and form communities, adapting to dynamic network conditions more effectively. Meanwhile, incorporating edge computing principles could significantly reduce latency and improve resource utilization. By distributing computation closer to vehicles, MIDCR could make more sophisticated routing decisions based on locally processed data. Future work will also involve benchmarking MIDCR against newer protocols like CTDHR and MMHNA under real-world deployments.

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Authors' Profiles

Pasupula Praveen Yadav received his Bachelor of Technology in Computer Science and Information Technology from Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University, Hyderabad (T.S.) INDIA in 2006; Master of Technology in Computer Science and Engineering from Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University, Ananthapuram (A.P.) INDIA in 2014. He is pursuing his Ph.D. in the area of Artificial Intelligence and IoT under Faculty of Computer Science and Technology at Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur (A.P), INDIA. He has 15 years of teaching experience. He is working as Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering in G Pulla Reddy Engineering College, Kurnool (A.P) India. His current research interests include Edge Computing, Service Computing and VANETS.

Dr. Thota Bhaskara Reddy is a Professor in the department of Computer Science and Technology at Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur (A.P.), INDIA. He has completed his M.Sc and Ph.D in computer science from S.K. University. He has acquired M.Tech from Nagarjuna University. He has been continuously imparting his knowledge to several students for the last 26 years. He has published 98 National and International publications. He has completed a major research project (UGC). Twenty One Ph.D and Three M.Phil have been awarded under his guidance. His research interests are in the field of Neural Networks, Image Processing, computer networks, data mining and data warehouse.

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